

Claremont Model for Information and Research Services Redesign¹

Philosophy of the Model:

- Patron-driven – *we provide services that our patrons want and need, in the manner in which they want and need to receive them.*
- Responsive, effective, friendly service to our users
- Foster self-sufficiency in users – *while we want to provide assistance to our users we also realize that in many instances, our users want to work independently, therefore we provide the means for users to navigate our website and utilize our resources as efficiently and easily as possible*
- Make the best use of technology to give excellent service – *our users expect the libraries to provide cutting edge technological resources; we also want to employ technology in the provision of reference and information services*
- Barrier-free – *includes the elimination of physical barriers as well as technological barriers as much as possible*
- Acknowledge “Generation Y” and their learning styles – *born after 1982, this generation expects information to be available whenever and wherever, they multitask and therefore expect all tools to be available wherever they are working, they are accustomed to an environment where life, play, entertainment, school and work commingle in an increasingly self service environment, they use instant messaging for recreation as well as educational purposes, they expect value and tend to be visual learners with low thresholds for boredom.*
- Provide seamless navigation of Libraries’ web site – *should be easy and logical to use*
- Provide seamless navigation of the libraries’ buildings – *excellent signage, and also provide personal service where needed*
- More opportunities for staff to choose to work with users – *there will be opportunities for staff to work in public service areas in addition to their primary responsibilities (e.g., Welcome desk)*
- Respect for each other’s work – *everyone’s job within the library is important and all need to be valued for their contribution to overall excellent service to our users*
- A structure that focuses on accountability – *all staff need to perform excellently and this needs to be expected as part of each member’s job*
- Establish collaboration points between IT and public services (both within IT and in the Search Centers) – *so much of what we do in public service areas involves technology that we need to establish close ties with IT, especially in the areas of development and innovation*
- Offer opportunities for users to provide continuous feedback of our services – *we need to provide methods for our users to comment on the service and services that are provided*
- Consistent training for all public service points – *one of the comments expressed by our users in the past has been inconsistent service from different staff members, with consistent training using uniform training materials, all staff should be able to provide equal information service*
- Everyone on the staff is in effect a “Roaming Information Provider”

¹ Completed 9/8/2004

Features of the Model

Physical features:

- Establish Research Services Desk staffed by either a Research Assistant and a Librarian, or just one of these, depending on time of day.
This desk might be staffed by 2 Research Assistants during morning, evening and weekend hours when there is no reference librarian on duty, so that one Assistant could be roving through the building.
- Eliminate present location of Reference Desk
In this model, the Reference Desk would be combined with the present Information Desk, to become a Research Services Desk. The Desk's location will ultimately be determined by other features of the model.
- Remove Search Center Assistants Desk,
Students currently in this position could become Research Assistants or Welcome Desk Assistants.
- *These positions could become either Research Services Desk Assistants, with part of their responsibility being to rove through the building, looking for people who need help. Another possibility is that the present job description for a library shelver may be expanded to include roving responsibilities – i.e., a shelver would have training to provide answers to directional questions and have an understanding of where to refer library users with various questions. Modules for this training will be developed, so that all staff have access to consistent training.*
- Establish a Welcome Desk (counter-height) in the lobby of Honnold/Mudd, to welcome users, scan cards and answer directional questions.
The primary purpose of the Welcome Desk is to scan cards, monitor the gates and the elevator exit, offer initial directional information and generally welcome people to the library. Potential security issues here could be addressed by the installation of a "panic button" under the desk counter, use of a security camera and/or use of an emergency telephone. Also, this configuration would allow the elevator to be used for access to all floors of the building. This type of gate would free the Research Services Assistants at the Research Services Desks from oversight of the gate.
- Establish kiosks with a pc and phone (direct line to Research Services Desk) on Honnold 1st floor and Mudd 1st floor (2 kiosks on each floor, side-by-side, 1 stand-up height and one that meets ADA requirements) and at Denison and Sprague.
This would establish a needed presence in these areas of the buildings, from which questions are often generated.
- Copy Center moves to present ILL/Document Delivery area
This would provide a more public presence for the Copy Center as well as provide Copy Center support for the networked printers
- Move networked printer from its present location in H/M Search Center to the area across from the new Copy Center; Copy Center staff have responsibility for printers.
Copy Center staff will be able to keep this public printer in their line of vision to monitor its service.
- Open Copy Center/Multi-Media Room area by knocking out wall between the 2 and reconfigure the space as needed.
- Move multi-media equipment out into open area across from Copy Center (except for plotter); some of the present pc's would move to south Index Room.

We have observed in other libraries that multi-media equipment is used more when it is not behind the physical barrier of a door. Students seem to appreciate being “empowered” to make use of this equipment without intervention.

- Move some A/V materials to public area (present Index Room? Near MMR?); process these with specialized tattletape for security.
Users appreciate the ability to browse these materials and select what they need.
- Open present Index Room (New Library 2nd floor, South) to add PCs and comfortable furniture, Browsing & New Books, newspapers.
This would provide a welcoming area for a variety of purposes, as the user enters the building. Lighting is good, and people already make frequent use of the study tables in this area.
- Circulation Desk will become the “Circulation and Information” service point, with responsibility for answering more telephone calls and making more referrals.
With the consolidation of the Reference Desk, Information Desk and the Search Center Assistance Desk into one Research Services Desk, this will allow only 2 major desks for patrons to choose between, rather than 4. Also, since many questions that presently come to the Information Desk are transferred to Circulation, this change in telephone lines will provide smoother service for our patrons.

Technology features (enhancements and/or changes):

- Monitor 24/7 for Claremont Colleges users more hours; recommendation is to monitor Claremont Colleges users all the hours the Research Services Desk is staffed with a reference librarian.
This allows Claremont users instant response from a Claremont librarian, rather than experiencing the delay inherent in email; 24/7 software responses would still be available other hours from librarians at other 24/7 institutions.
- Put “Do you need help?” button in prominent place on main web site page, as well as on other web pages, with immediate responses expected.
This button could appear on all our web pages that include the “Libraries of the Claremont Colleges” banner, as well as on other pages that could be constructed to include the button [Note: it is uncertain whether or not we can place this button within commercial databases to which we subscribe.] The button would connect to the 24/7 software, which would be monitored by Claremont librarians during the hours there is a reference librarian on duty.
- Brand our electronic resources
By doing this, we let our users know that they are “in” the library virtually, and that these are resources that we have deliberately subscribed to or otherwise made accessible for their use.
- Implement OpenURL
This allows the user to make a direct connection to the full text of an item if we have electronic access to it.
- Add continuous survey feedback form to web site, possibly as part of the “Do you need help” button options
This would serve as an additional means of input from our users, regarding help they might need, or comments they wish to make.
- Install CJK in Search Centers
We know from users’ comments that many of our user community would like the ability to have web pages display in Chinese, Japanese or Korean languages. This is a service application that is available to us and needs to be implemented.

- Electronic rolodex
The rolodex would be populated with questions and answers that staff have determined are important and/or for which the answers are esoteric and hard-to-find.
- Headsets for Research Assistants to be in contact with Research Services Desk staff, and for use at Denison and Sprague (SGM?)
This service would allow Research Assistants to contact the Desk, as well as allow the Desk to contact Research Assistants to alert them to someone needing assistance away from the Desk.
- Create online training modules for continuous referral by all staff.
These modules would contain a self-testing feature. All staff that come in contact with users should be familiar with these modules. Examples of these training modules: Locations and Directions, Blais Training, Connection Issues (remote, wireless, wired), Databases – using the subject list, basic Colleges information (names, locations), Electronic Journals, Electronic Books, Interlibrary Loan and Link+, Circulation Basics, Access Basics, 24/7, Ask a Librarian, Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel.
- Create blog for news regarding status of databases, information services, other resources
It is hoped that by having a central repository for this type of internal library information, there would be a decrease in similar email messages.
- Offer laptop checkout for users
We would try this on a limited basis at first, to see if there is a need.
- Sell connection cables at Copy Center
- Automatic startup and shutdown of public computers
- Information kiosks in Periodicals, Microforms, and possibly offsite (Pitzer? CMC? KGI? CGU?)
This would establish a needed presence in these 2 areas of Honnold/Mudd, from which questions are often generated. Also, Pitzer, CMC, CGU and KGI do not have a library on their campuses, and this would contribute to outreach efforts.
- “Call button” to be on pc’s within the Honnold/Mudd building so desk staff will know location of person needing assistance
The button would alert the Research Services Desk to the user’s need for assistance, and direct the staff to that person.

Staffing features and opportunities:

- Create an IT presence or helpline for more immediate response to Search Center’s user needs; 2-4 p.m. on weekdays is recommended as a beginning.
This can be either an IT staffer physically present in the search center during posted hours or virtually available via a monitored helpline.
- Provide Library staff with the opportunity to become part of a Technology Development Team, working with the IT unit to examine new developments in technology and to be a liaison with all staff.
This would be a new standing team created to specifically facilitate staff/IT communication.
- Assign Copy Center responsibility for plotter as well as networked printers.
The suggested move of the Copy Center to the current I.L.L. office and the relocation of the network printer to the north rail of the multi-tier stack would shift oversight and assistance to the Copy Center staff.
- Establish Research Assistant position.

- This position will work closely with librarians at the Honnold/Mudd Research Services Desk to provide initial assistance in the use of the Libraries' resources; they will work at the Desk as well as rove through the building. These Assistants will follow established referral protocols for handing off specific reference needs to either a librarian at the desk or to an appropriate subject specialist. Research Assistants may be regular staff, or in some cases, part-time temporary staff.*
- Establish "Roving Staff" (Research Assistants) for peak hours, to look for users needing help; these staff will wear nametags and identifiable library vest. *One suggestion is that roving responsibilities be included in multiple job descriptions, e.g. shelvers, information assistants, research desk librarians.*
 - Establish 30-60 minute shifts at a Welcome desk/table in H/M *Those at this desk would monitor the entrance gates and provide directional assistance. All staff (including student staff) would be encouraged to spend at least 30 minutes per week at this desk. There would be no external phone line or computer.*
 - Someone will take responsibility for scheduling Welcome Desk shifts.
 - Research Services Desk is staffed with at least 1 Research Assistant and 1 Reference Librarian during "reference hours" (10-10 and some weekend hours) *Those at this desk would answer information and reference questions in addition to monitoring 24/7's Claremont users and responding to virtual and physical requests for assistance.*
 - When no Reference Librarian is on duty, the desk is staffed with 2 Research Assistants, so that one may rove.
 - Transfer Search Center Assistants budget to budget for part-time temporary Research Assistants.
 - Librarians will self-select into Core Groups. Those in each Group will devote more specific time to that chosen function, and less to the other functional areas; by focusing on these areas, librarians will be able to address the feelings of being overworked and pulled in too many directions. Each group is responsible for developing training modules, policies and tools to assist all librarians with their tasks in these areas.

Assistance strategies:

- Staff is always "on call" and is expected to respond when called– *our users are our first priority*
- Roving staff ("Research Assistants") are scheduled during peak hours of library use – *this assistance will address the issue of our confusing and large building*
- 24/7 used more hours to monitor Claremont community – *with additional advertising, more opportunities for users to find the service, and excellent response time, usage of this service will hopefully rise*
- Everyone makes referrals – *throughout the library everyone should know who to refer users to in order to address their research needs*
- Heavier use of referral forms at desk, if subject specialist is not available – *when a user is referred to a subject specialist, the information/reference staff also fill out a referral slip to be given to the librarian so the librarian can make the contact and does not have to wait for the user to make the contact.*
- More actively pursue follow-up contacts with users helped at desks or online – *when a referral slip is passed on to someone else for follow-up, that person will contact the user within 24 hours*

- Provide scheduled, advertised, on site assistance at campuses (e.g., Pitzer, CMC, KGI)
- Create an IT service point – *a virtual service point that is staffed by IT personnel or IT trained students to respond to public service requests for assistance*
- Establishment of the kiosks on Honnold 1st floor and New Library 1st floor

Process Map

Information & Reference Services Redesign Model

7/26/2004

Illustration of Service Points

Claremont Training Module Possibilities
Provided for all staff who provide assistance
Available in both online and print formats
Includes self-testing component

From the Website

- *Blais*
- *eResearch Tools* : Research guides by subject, Databases, Electronic journals, Digital collections, Library catalogs, Quick facts & ready reference
- *Online Help*: Ask a librarian (incl. 24/7), Research strategies & tips, Course/program-specific help, Workshops & tours
- *Services & Policies*: Reference & instruction services, Services for faculty & students, Accessing our resources, Policies, The Copy Center
- *Hours & Locations*: Hours, The Libraries: Honnold/Mudd - Denison - Sprague - Seeley G. Mudd, Asian Studies collection, Special Collections , Maps & driving directions
- *Checking out materials*, Course reserves, E-books, Media materials, Request materials not at Claremont (InterLibrary Loan)
- *About the Libraries*: News, events & exhibits, Addresses & contact info, Job opportunities, Publications, Mission & goals, Library partners & affiliates
- *Quick Links*: Ask a librarian, My Blais account, LINK+, ERes, New books in the Libraries, Web search engines, The Claremont Colleges, Search our site, Government Publications
- *"How Do I..."*: Find materials in our collections, Find articles in journals, Find government information, Find electronic reserves, Find materials on reserve at our circulation desks, Access library resources from home and on campus, Make photocopies, Contact the Libraries

Additional Suggestions

- *Referrals*: Names and places at the Libraries, the Colleges, and CUC (directories/catalogs)
- *Event/Class Schedule Information*: Libraries, Colleges, and CUC calendars, combined class schedule
- *Maps/Location Guides*: Libraries, Colleges, and CUC
- *Service Points' Policies, Protocols, Procedures and Forms*
- *Reference Interview/Assistance Strategies*: Coordinating the work of librarians/assistants
- *Shelving Basics*
- *Microforms*
- *Equipment*: workstations, monitors, network printer, storage devices (zip, floppy, usb), multimedia equipment (including workstations, scanners, audio playback, and video/DVD viewers)
- *Software*: Internet Explorer, Microsoft Office (Word, Excel, Access, Power Point), GIS, and multimedia applications
- *Connectivity*: wired, wireless, remote

**Model: Information & Research Services Redesign
Progress Report 6/14/2005**

T=Target, O=Off Target

<i>Philosophy: Objective</i>	T/ O	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
Patron-driven – <i>we provide services that our patrons want and need, in the manner in which they want and need to receive them.</i>	T	Staff members ask more often if what we are doing is best for our patrons
Responsive, effective, friendly service to our users	T	Service has been incorporated into our SWOT exercises.
Foster self-sufficiency in users – <i>while we want to provide assistance to our users we also realize that in many instances, our users want to work independently, therefore we provide the means for users to navigate our website and utilize our resources as efficiently and easily as possible</i>	O	Ways to foster self sufficiency: hand outs (wait until the Publications assistant arrives?), website (library awareness is working on), signage (Kelley will talk to Library awareness)
Make the best use of technology to give excellent service – <i>our users expect the libraries to provide cutting edge technological resources; we also want to employ technology in the provision of reference and information services</i>	T	Computers have been upgraded, the multi media equipment has been moved to an open area, new digital microform reader and printer, “Claremont Cash” will be accepted at the Copy Center to pay fines and purchase Copy Center items starting Fall 2005.
Barrier-free – <i>includes the elimination of physical barriers as well as technological barriers as much as possible</i>	T	The elevator has been opened up to all floors, the Welcome Desk helps people at the entrance, extra wireless hubs have been installed, extra ports have been activated. Ina will talk to Jusef about having a computer with handicapped access. Future steps: more joint planning between IT and Libraries’ staff should take place.

<i>Philosophy: Objective</i>	T/ O	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
Acknowledge "Generation Y" and their learning styles – <i>born after 1982, this generation expects information to be available whenever and wherever, they multitask and therefore expect all tools to be available wherever they are working, they are accustomed to an environment where life, play, entertainment, school and work commingle in an increasingly self service environment, they use instant messaging for recreation as well as educational purposes, they expect value and tend to be visual learners with low thresholds for boredom.</i>	T	Effort was made to acknowledge "GenerationY" by including students in our committee, reading articles about their learning styles, and attending conferences that covered this topic.
Provide seamless navigation of Libraries' web site – <i>should be easy and logical to use</i>	T	Library Awareness is redesigning webpage, modified version due Fall 2005, Blais retooling group SPT is examining the design of our online catalog. Future steps: continue to look at the website with focus groups and other assessment tools.
Provide seamless navigation of the libraries' buildings – <i>excellent signage, and also provide personal service where needed</i>	O	Need to create signage and discuss navigation. Kelley will talk to Library Awareness.
More opportunities for staff to choose to work with users – <i>there will be opportunities for staff to work in public service areas in addition to their primary responsibilities (e.g., Welcome desk)</i>	T	Staff have the opportunity to work at the Welcome Desk, staff will have the same opportunity at the Information and Reference Desk Fall 2005.
Respect for each other's work – <i>everyone's job within the library is important and all need to be valued for their contribution to overall excellent service to our users</i>	T	Respect has been incorporated into a SWOT group.
A structure that focuses on accountability – <i>all staff need to perform excellently and this needs to be expected as part of each member's job</i>	O	Beyond the scope of our charge.

<i>Philosophy: Objective</i>	<i>T/ O</i>	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
Establish collaboration points between IT and public services (both within IT and in the Search Centers) – <i>so much of what we do in public service areas involves technology that we need to establish close ties with IT, especially in the areas of development and innovation</i>	T	IT staff member now has office in the search center. Future steps: IT staff member will be incorporated more into the information and reference staff by including him in meetings, joining him to mail list, having him staff the information desk. <u>Cindy</u> will talk to IT about this.
Offer opportunities for users to provide continuous feedback of our services – <i>we need to provide methods for our users to comment on the service and services that are provided</i>	O	<u>Kelley</u> will talk to Library Awareness
Consistent training for all public service points – <i>one of the comments expressed by our users in the past has been inconsistent service from different staff members, with consistent training using uniform training materials, all staff should be able to provide equal information service</i>	O	<u>Cindy</u> will write proposal for an integrated public service training program, proposal will be brought to management council with the recommendation that an SPT be formed
Everyone on the staff is in effect a “Roaming Information Provider”	O	Staff now have name tags and shirts with libraries’ logo to make more visible to patrons. Future steps: <u>Cindy</u> will address this in proposal in point above.

<i>Physical Features: Objective</i>	<i>T/ O</i>	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
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<i>Physical Features: Objective</i>	T/ O	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
<p>Establish Research Services Desk staffed by either a Research Assistant and a Librarian, or just one of these, depending on time of day. <i>This desk might be staffed by 2 Research Assistants during morning, evening and weekend hours when there is no reference librarian on duty, so that one Assistant could be roving through the building.</i></p>	T	<p>The reference and information desk is now staffed by a combination of librarian and information assistant. Due to budget constraint and thus shortage of information assistants, roving is not possible at this point. Also, some staffing issues need to be worked out. Cindy will send a message to Ref Desk mail list and form a group of Iris librarians to look at the librarian staffing issues at the desk.</p>
<p>Eliminate present location of Reference Desk <i>In this model, the Reference Desk would be combined with the present Information Desk, to become a Research Services Desk. The Desk's location will ultimately be determined by other features of the model.</i></p>	T	<p>Old desks have been moved to new location, waiting for new desk to be installed.</p>
<p>Remove Search Center Assistants Desk, <i>Students currently in this position could become Research Assistants or Welcome Desk Assistants. These positions could become either Research Services Desk Assistants, with part of their responsibility being to rove through the building, looking for people who need help. Another possibility is that the present job description for a library shelver may be expanded to include roving responsibilities – i.e., a shelver would have training to provide answers to directional questions and have an understanding of where to refer library users with various questions. Modules for this training will be developed, so that all staff have access to consistent training.</i></p>	T	<p>Due to budget constraints, shelvers cannot be rovers at this point, however they will receive information assistant training.</p>

<i>Physical Features: Objective</i>	<i>T/ O</i>	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
<p>Establish a Welcome Desk (counter-height) in the lobby of Honnold/Mudd, to welcome users, scan cards and answer directional questions. <i>The primary purpose of the Welcome Desk is to scan cards, monitor the gates and the elevator exit, offer initial directional information and generally welcome people to the library. Potential security issues here could be addressed by the installation of a "panic button" under the desk counter, use of a security camera and/or use of an emergency telephone. Also, this configuration would allow the elevator to be used for access to all floors of the building. This type of gate would free the Research Services Assistants at the Research Services Desks from oversight of the gate.</i></p>	T	<p>Temporary Welcome Desk is in place, due to costs and time required, new desk will not be installed until summer 2006, earliest.</p>
<p>Establish kiosks with a pc and phone (direct line to Research Services Desk) on Honnold 1st floor and Mudd 1st floor (2 kiosks on each floor, side-by-side, 1 stand-up height and one that meets ADA requirements) and at Denison and Sprague. <i>This would establish a needed presence in these areas of the buildings, from which questions are often generated.</i></p>	O	<p>We need to investigate this further. Both floors are currently under renovation, recommendations are being postponed until completion.</p>
<p>Copy Center moves to present ILL/Document Delivery area <i>This would provide a more public presence for the Copy Center as well as provide Copy Center support for the networked printers</i></p>	T	
<p>Move networked printer from its present location in H/M Search Center to the area across from the new Copy Center; Copy Center staff have responsibility for printers. <i>Copy Center staff will be able to keep this public printer in their line of vision to monitor its service.</i></p>	T	

<i>Physical Features: Objective</i>	T/ O	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
Open Copy Center/Multi-Media Room area by knocking out wall between the 2 and reconfigure the space as needed.	T	
Move multi-media equipment out into open area across from Copy Center (except for plotter); some of the present pc's would move to south Index Room. <i>We have observed in other libraries that multi-media equipment is used more when it is not behind the physical barrier of a door. Students seem to appreciate being "empowered" to make use of this equipment without intervention.</i>	T	Multi-media equipment now in search center.
Move some A/V materials to public area (present Index Room? Near MMR?); process these with specialized tattletale for security. <i>Users appreciate the ability to browse these materials and select what they need.</i>	O	Due to security concerns, this is not being done at this time. Consider option in the future.
Open present Index Room (New Library 2 nd floor, South) to add pc's and comfortable furniture, Browsing & New Books, newspapers. <i>This would provide a welcoming area for a variety of purposes, as the user enters the building. Lighting is good, and people already make frequent use of the study tables in this area.</i>	T	Browsing and new books were not moved due to lack of space. Still hope to get comfortable furniture in the search center.
Circulation Desk will become the "Circulation and Information" service point, with responsibility for answering more telephone calls and making more referrals. <i>With the consolidation of the Reference Desk, Information Desk and the Search Center Assistance Desk into one Research Services Desk, this will allow only 2 major desks for patrons to choose between, rather than 4. Also, since many questions that presently come to the Information Desk are transferred to Circulation, this change in telephone lines will provide smoother service for our patrons.</i>	O	Circulation staff will receive public service training at a future date when public service training program is implemented. Also, Fall semester circulation and the information/reference desk will survey phone calls to decide what phone line would best serve our patrons. Cindy will implement the survey with Marcia and Circulation.

<i>Technology Features: Objective</i>	<i>T/ O</i>	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
<p>Monitor 24/7 for Claremont Colleges users more hours; recommendation is to monitor Claremont Colleges users all the hours the Research Services Desk is staffed with a reference librarian. <i>This allows Claremont users instant response from a Claremont librarian, rather than experiencing the delay inherent in email; 24/7 software responses would still be available other hours from librarians at other 24/7 institutions.</i></p>	O	<p>Cindy will send message to Ref Desk mail list reminding people to turn 24/7 on while at the reference desk. She will also place a sign on the reference desk.</p>
<p>Put "Do you need help?" button in prominent place on main web site page, as well as on other web pages, with immediate responses expected. <i>This button could appear on all our web pages that include the "Libraries of the Claremont Colleges" banner, as well as on other pages that could be constructed to include the button [Note: it is uncertain whether or not we can place this button within commercial databases to which we subscribe.] The button would connect to the 24/7 software, which would be monitored by Claremont librarians during the hours there is a reference librarian on duty.</i></p>	O	<p>Cindy will talk to IT to see if this is possible.</p>
<p>Brand our electronic resources. <i>By doing this, we let our users know that they are "in" the library virtually, and that these are resources that we have deliberately subscribed to or otherwise made accessible for their use.</i></p>	T	<p>This is an ongoing project. Kelley will ask Cindi for the status of this.</p>
<p>Implement OpenURL <i>This allows the user to make a direct connection to the full text of an item if we have electronic access to it.</i></p>	T	<p>Open URL group is ongoing.</p>
<p>Add continuous survey feedback form to web site, possibly as part of the "Do you need help" button options <i>This would serve as an additional means of input from our users, regarding help they might need, or comments they wish to make.</i></p>	O	<p>Kelley will ask Cindi about this.</p>

<i>Technology Features: Objective</i>	T/ O	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
<i>Install CJK in Search Centers We know from users' comments that many of our user community would like the ability to have web pages display in Chinese, Japanese or Korean languages. This is a service application that is available to us and needs to be implemented.</i>	T	Language utility has been turned on.
<i>Electronic rolodex The rolodex would be populated with questions and answers that staff have determined are important and/or for which the answers are esoteric and hard-to-find.</i>	T	Rolodex in place, but we need to encourage staff to use it. Ina will hold an inservice training session and ask people if they find it useful.
<i>Headsets for Research Assistants to be in contact with Research Services Desk staff, and for use at Denison and Sprague (SGM?) This service would allow Research Assistants to contact the Desk, as well as allow the Desk to contact Research Assistants to alert them to someone needing assistance away from the Desk.</i>	T	Headsets purchased, do we need to train staff when to use them and what they are for?
<i>Create online training modules for continuous referral by all staff. These modules would contain a self-testing feature. All staff that come in contact with users should be familiar with these modules. Examples of these training modules: Locations and Directions, Blais Training, Connection Issues (remote, wireless, wired), Databases – using the subject list, basic Colleges information (names, locations), Electronic Journals, Electronic Books, Interlibrary Loan and Link+, Circulation Basics, Access Basics, 24/7, Ask a Librarian, Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel.</i>	O	Cindy will incorporate this into the proposal for an integrated public service training program.
<i>Create blog for news regarding status of databases, information services, other resources It is hoped that by having a central repository for this type of internal library information, there would be a decrease in similar email messages.</i>	?	Start here next meeting What is the status of this?

<i>Technology Features: Objective</i>	<i>T/ O</i>	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
Offer laptop checkout for users <i>We would try this on a limited basis at first, to see if there is a need.</i>	O	Are we still planning on doing this? In focus groups, idea got mixed review.
Sell connection cables at Copy Center	T	
Automatic startup and shutdown of public computers	?	
Information kiosks in Periodicals, Microforms, and possibly offsite (Pitzer? CMC? KGI? CGU?) <i>This would establish a needed presence in these 2 areas of Honnold/Mudd, from which questions are often generated. Also, Pitzer, CMC, CGU and KGI do not have a library on their campuses, and this would contribute to outreach efforts.</i>	O	Create plan to implement; same point addressed in "physical features"
"Call button" to be on PC's within the Honnold/Mudd building so desk staff will know location of person needing assistance <i>The button would alert the Research Services Desk to the user's need for assistance, and direct the staff to that person.</i>	O	Discuss with IT?

<i>Staffing Features and Opportunities: Objective</i>	<i>T/ O</i>	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
Create an IT presence or helpline for more immediate response to Search Center's user needs; 2-4 p.m. on weekdays is recommended as a beginning. <i>This can be either an IT staffer physically present in the search center during posted hours or virtually available via a monitored helpline.</i>	T	

Staffing Features and Opportunities: Objective	T/ O	Next Steps and Comments
Provide Library staff with the opportunity to become part of a Technology Development Team, working with the IT unit to examine new developments in technology and to be a liaison with all staff. <i>This would be a new standing team created to specifically facilitate staff/IT communication.</i>	O	Are we abandoning this plan? Why?
Assign Copy Center responsibility for plotter as well as networked printers. <i>The suggested move of the Copy Center to the current I.L.L. office and the relocation of the network printer to the north rail of the multi-tier stack would shift oversight and assistance to the Copy Center staff.</i>	T	
Establish Research Assistant position. <i>This position will work closely with librarians at the Honnold/Mudd Research Services Desk to provide initial assistance in the use of the Libraries' resources; they will work at the Desk as well as rove through the building. These Assistants will follow established referral protocols for handing off specific reference needs to either a librarian at the desk or to an appropriate subject specialist. Research Assistants may be regular staff, or in some cases, part-time temporary staff.</i>	T	Are we encouraging regular staff to sit at this desk?
Establish "Roving Staff" (Research Assistants) for peak hours, to look for users needing help; these staff will wear nametags and identifiable library vest. <i>One suggestion is that roving responsibilities be included in multiple job descriptions, e.g. shelvers, information assistants, research desk librarians.</i>	O	Will we be implementing Roving Staff?

<i>Staffing Features and Opportunities: Objective</i>	<i>T/ O</i>	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
<p>Establish 30-60 minute shifts at a Welcome desk/table in H/M <i>Those at this desk would monitor the entrance gates and provide directional assistance. All staff (including student staff) would be encouraged to spend at least 30 minutes per week at this desk. There would be no external phone line or computer.</i></p>	T	
<p>Someone will take responsibility for scheduling Welcome Desk shifts.</p>	T	
<p>Research Services Desk is staffed with at least 1 Research Assistant and 1 Reference Librarian during “reference hours” (10-10 and some weekend hours) <i>Those at this desk would answer information and reference questions in addition to monitoring 24/7’s Claremont users and responding to virtual and physical requests for assistance.</i></p>	?	
<p>When no Reference Librarian is on duty, the desk is staffed with 2 Research Assistants, so that one may rove.</p>	?	
<p>Transfer Search Center Assistants budget to budget for part-time temporary Research Assistants.</p>	T	
<p>Librarians will self-select into Core Groups. Those in each Group will devote more specific time to that chosen function, and less to the other functional areas; by focusing on these areas, librarians will be able to address the feelings of being overworked and pulled in too many directions. Each group is responsible for developing training modules, policies and tools to assist all librarians with their tasks in these areas.</p>	O	<p>This objective was decided to be out of scope for the reference redesign team and is being examined by the Librarians group</p>

<i>Assistance Strategies: Objective</i>	<i>T/ O</i>	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
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<i>Assistance Strategies: Objective</i>	<i>T/ O</i>	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
Staff is always “on call” and is expected to respond when called– <i>our users are our first priority</i>	?	
Roving staff (“Research Assistants”) are scheduled during peak hours of library use – <i>this assistance will address the issue of our confusing and large building</i>	O	
24/7 used more hours to monitor Claremont community – <i>with additional advertising, more opportunities for users to find the service, and excellent response time, usage of this service will hopefully rise</i>	O	
Everyone makes referrals – <i>throughout the library everyone should know who to refer users to in order to address their research needs</i>	?	
Heavier use of referral forms at desk, if subject specialist is not available – <i>when a user is referred to a subject specialist, the information/reference staff also fill out a referral slip to be given to the librarian so the librarian can make the contact and does not have to wait for the user to make the contact.</i>	?	
More actively pursue follow-up contacts with users helped at desks or online – <i>when a referral slip is passed on to someone else for follow-up, that person will contact the user within 24 hours</i>	?	
Provide scheduled, advertised, on site assistance at campuses (e.g., Pitzer, CMC, KGI)	O	Are we going to pursue this?
Create an IT service point – <i>a virtual service point that is staffed by IT personnel or IT trained students to respond to public service requests for assistance</i>	?	

<i>Assistance Strategies: Objective</i>	<i>T/ O</i>	<i>Next Steps and Comments</i>
Establishment of the kiosks on Honnold 1 st floor and New Library 1 st floor	O	Create plan to implement; also addressed in “physical features” and “technology features”

Claremont Initial Student Survey

	<p>Please fill out our survey and help us improve our services!</p>
---	--

Your affiliation:

<input type="checkbox"/> CMC <input type="checkbox"/> Harvey Mudd <input type="checkbox"/> Pitzer <input type="checkbox"/> Pomona <input type="checkbox"/> Scripps <input type="checkbox"/> CGU <input type="checkbox"/> KGI <input type="checkbox"/> CUC	<input type="checkbox"/> Undergrad <input type="checkbox"/> Graduate <input type="checkbox"/> Faculty <input type="checkbox"/> Staff
--	---

1. Do you use the Libraries' website from your dorm/home?

Yes No

If yes, how often?

Daily Once a Week Once a Month or less

2. Do you use the Libraries as a study space?

Yes No

Which one(s)?

Denison Honnold/Mudd Seeley G. Mudd Sprague

What would make you want to study there more often?

3. If the libraries offered laptop computers for checkout for use within the building, would you use this service?

Yes No

4. When using the Libraries, do you usually find what you are looking for?

Yes No

If no, what types of difficulties do you often have?

5. The Librarians offer many different types of assistance to help you with your research. Which of the following have you used? What would you be likely to use if you needed help? Please mark all that apply.

Assistance at the Reference Desk
 have used would use if needed help

Email with a Librarian
 have used would use if needed help

Telephone with a Librarian
 have used would use if needed help

Make an appointment with a Librarian
 have used would use if needed help

24/7 Online Chat with a Librarian
 have used would use if needed help

6. How can the Libraries improve service? What would most help you with your research?

Give us your opinion and earn some \$\$\$!

Would you be willing to participate in a one-hour Focus Group in late October to discuss enhanced and improved Research services at the Libraries? (You would receive a stipend and refreshments for participating.)

Yes No

If yes, how may we contact you?

Name:

Phone:

Email:

Initial Student Survey Findings

December 6th, 2004

Total Number of Surveys: 488

Affiliation	Number of Participants	Undergraduate	Graduate	Faculty	Staff	More than one
CGU:	55	0	53	1	1	0
CGU/CUC:	1	0	0	0	0	1
CMC:	104	102	0	1	1	0
CMC/CUC:	1	0	0	0	1	0
CUC:	3	0	0	0	3	0
Harvey Mudd:	62	62	0	0	0	0
Pitzer:	76	72	0	1	2	1
Pomona:	97	95	0	2	0	0
Scripps	89	86	0	3	0	0
TOTAL	487	417	52	8	8	2

Affiliation of Survey Respondents

1.) Do you use the Libraries' website from your dorm/home?

Yes: 388 (80%)

No: 100 (20%)

1.) a.) If yes, how often?

Once a month or less: 165 (34%)

Once a week: 193 (40%)

Daily: 40 (8%)

N/A: 90 (18%)

2.) Do you use the Libraries as a study space?

Yes: 269 (55%)

No: 219 (45%)

Which one(s)?

2a.) Denison: 81

2b.) Honnold/Mudd: 246

2c.) Seeley G. Mudd: 27

2d.) Sprague: 32

2e.) What would make you want to study there more often?

Themes

-Left Blank: 186

-Furniture (Couches, Tables, Swing Chairs, Lamps): 64

-Closer: 60

-Nothing (Library is Fine as is, I am lazy): 55

-Hours: 27

-Food & Drink: 24

-Study Areas: 20

-Other (Music, TV): 20

-Lighting: 17

-Computers/Laptops: 15

-Internet: 13

-Quieter: 9

-Temperature (Warmer): 10

-Items (Highlighters, Dry Erase Boards): 4

-Less Quiet: 3

-Services (More Periodical, Pleasure Reading): 1

3.) If the libraries offered laptop computers for checkout for use within the building, would you use this service?

Yes: 190 (39%)

No: 294 (60%)
N/a: 4 (1%)

4.) When using the Libraries, do you usually find what you are looking for?

Yes: 430 (88%)
No: 47 (10%)
N/a: 11 (2%)

4a.) If no, what types of difficulties do you often have?

Themes:

-N/A: 421
-Locating Books: 25
-Periodicals: 15
-Locating Areas (Finding the location): 8
-Finding Items I need: 7
-Using Link + (Use it too often): 4
-Computer Gives Wrong Information: 2
-Databases (confusing): 2
-Searching Specific Topics: 2
-Call Numbers: 1

5.) The Librarians offer many different types of assistance to help you with your research. Which of the following have you used? What would you be likely to use if you needed help? Please mark all that apply.

5a.) Assistance at the Reference Desk:

Have used: 362 (74%)
Would use if needed help: 112 (23%)
N/a: 14 (3%)

5b.) Email with a Librarian

Have used: 100 (20%)
Would use if needed help: 310 (64%)
N/a: 78 (16%)

5c.) Telephone with a Librarian

Have used: 66 (14%)
Would use if needed help: 277 (56%)
N/a: 145 (30%)

5d.) Make an appointment with a Librarian

Have used: 60 (12%)
Would use if needed help: 295 (60%)
N/a: 133 (28%)

5e.) 24/7 Online Chat with a Librarian

Have used: 11 (2%)

Would use if needed help: 294 (60%)

N/a: 183 (38%)

6.) How can the Libraries improve service? What would most help you with your research?

Improve:

-You are doing a great Job as is: 39

-Expand Collection: 26

-Online Services: 21

-Directions: 3

-Hours: 10

-Tutorials: 8

-Advertising of Services: 8

-Processes: 9

-Research Assistance: 12

-Databases: 4

-Other: 9

-Design: 5

-Internet: 3

-Maps: 5

-Book Return: 3

-Furniture: 5

-Quieter: 2

-Remote Access: 3

-Search Options: 1

-Food: 1

-Lighting: 1

-Printing: 3

**Claremont Focus Group Findings
December 6, 2004**

Demographics

-Total Participants: 22

-Gender:

Females: 13

Males: 9

-Affiliation:

Claremont Graduate University: 10

Claremont McKenna: 2

Claremont University Consortium: 1

Harvey Mudd: 1

Keck Graduate Institute: 1

Pitzer: 2

Pomona: 4

Scripps: 1

-Standing:

Faculty: 5

Freshman: 2

Sophomore: 1

Junior: 2

Senior: 1

Graduate: 10

Post-graduate: 1

-Area of Specialization:

Anthropology: 1

Biology: 1

Biotechnology: 1

Evaluation/Applied Methods: 1

Evaluation/Organizational Behavior: 1

Higher Education: 1

History: 1

Humanities/Cultural Studies: 1

International Relations: 1

Illustrated Storytelling: 1

Literature: 1

Media Studies/Mathematics: 1

MBA: 1

Organizational Behavior: 1

Political Science: 2

Psychology: 2

Religious Studies: 1

SBOS: 1

STS: 1
Women's Studies: 1

-Live on Campus:

Yes: 7
No: 15

-If you live off campus, how long does it take you to get to the Claremont Colleges?

No answer: 2
0-5 minutes: 1
5-10 minutes: 7
11-30 minutes: 5

-Do you own a computer?

Yes: 21
No: 1

-If "no" do you have access to a computer?

N/A: 21
Yes: 1

Focus Group Questions: Major Themes

What do you think about the entrance to the Honnold/Mudd building? What is good, bad, or needs improvement?

Good:

-Look:
The library glitters at night
The lighting is nice

Bad:

-Entrance:
Difficult to find
No entrance to Honnold side
Lobby is boring, oppressive
Confusing
Inconvenient
Unfriendly/uninviting
Ugly
Wasted space
Turnstiles are a barrier

-Design/Look:

Unfriendly/uninviting
Institutional
Floor signage is confusing
Desks labels can be clearer

-Accessibility:

No accessible parking
Unclear path at night
Book return not very accessible/visible

Purpose/Direction:

No Services in lobby
No direction
Counterintuitive

Use of ID Card:

Barrier

Needs Improvement:

-Entrance:

Handles on handicap doors
More Spectacular
More than one entrance
Person in lobby to welcome you
Signs
Move Turnstiles in lobby
One door at the entrance instead of two
Close off Bridge and create large entrance
Art
Larger Library sign on top of bridge

-Design/Look:

More outside study areas
There should be large (brass) letters on the building
A theme of the month
Grand staircase and lions

-Use of ID Card:

Hard to remember my card
Don't think we should have to use the card

Once here what is the first thing you usually do when you enter?

-Find Individuals:

Find my group – classmates

-Find a location:

Find a study place
Try to find a quiet place

If you need help at the library, do you find the help easily? Are you helped by a library staff member, or electronically (both or neither)? Who do you ask if you need research help? Do you receive the help you need?

-Information Desk

-Librarians

-Electronic:

Online Services/Journals
Website
Inter Library

Email reference

-Other:

Maps

-Positive:

Librarians help promptly

-Can Improve:

Many possible location of items

Expand GIS

Books move around

Old materials difficult to obtain

Do you receive help promptly?

-Positive:

Experience with staff very positive

Love databases – good search

Use copy center a lot

Use newspapers

Like study rooms

Like research center

Can you identify staff members easily? If not, what would make them more identifiable? If staff were easier to identify, would you be more likely to ask them for help (if needed)?

-Positive:

Staff are identifiable by the props they are using

Calling by name sets up a relationship

-Can Improve:

Nametags would be helpful

Student staff don't know answers

What kind of assistance would you find most helpful? Staff at a desk?

-Yes:

Reference desk

Reference staff

Librarians

-Can Improve:

3rd and 4th floor old computers

Better Maps

Location information could be added to blais – “if you are here – go here”

Better wireless

Clearer labeling

Staff in the stacks?

-Yes:

If people were available on each floor all the time

The shelver has helped me in the past

Staff who would go with you to help you find materials?

-Yes:

- Like staff going with you
- They already do this
- If shelveers had a way of getting information

Information kiosks?

-Yes:

- Telephone in kiosk might be helpful

-No:

- Unnecessary

Roving staff?

-Yes:

- I still get lost
- Would maximize my efficiency
- Lots of times I would have liked being approached

-No:

- Would be intrusive
- Don't like people watching me
- Maybe not the best use of funds
- Better to have staff at central area/location
- Keep library staff in one central area

Are there any bad locations in the library?

-Locating Items/Signs

- Labeling is not clear
- Constant shifting – annoying

-Design:

- Multi-tier stacks
- This is by far the most complicated library I have ever used
- Disjointed

-Can Improve:

- Orientation to library
- Ongoing library tours
- Computers on different floors

-Locations that need improvement

- Re-shelving area
- Government Documents
- K's
- Microform
- History section
- Basement organized oddly
- Multi-tier stacks
- Microfiche/film

Health/Medicine area
Videos

What is your opinion of the Libraries web site? (Show them a visual of the homepage) Do you find resources and links easily or with difficulty?

-Good:

One of the better college websites that I have used (from a web designer)
User friendly

-Bad:

Not intuitive
Cluttered

-Can Improve:

When you are off campus, the back button bumps you off
Keep Main Menu--all other menus could be collapsed
Customize access to website

The libraries are considering placing a “Do you need help” button on the website – where should it be placed so that it will be most visible?

-Location:

The upper right third
Top right
Center (top or bottom)
Set apart (to stand out)

-Color/Image:

A flashing button might be annoying
Cool blue would be inviting
Should be red – blue blends in

The libraries are considering purchasing software that would install a “call button” on each public library computer. When activated (by you) a reference desk staff person would come to you. Would this be helpful/useful? Why or why not? Would you use it?

-Good/Would use it:

Some people's first experience with a computer is in the library
Needed a lot of help
Anything that allows students to be more efficient
Would work well with a FAQ section

-No/Would not use it:

It would be like an airplane
It is not necessary
Doesn't seem all that efficient
Staff is willing and excited to help students

Do the computers in the libraries have all of the programs/software that you need to complete your work? If not, what are they lacking?

-Yes:

Very time efficient
GIS
Remote services like e-journals
Databases, Link+, ILL

-Can Add:

Search all the databases at one time, called Academic Search Premier
More titles

Would you be interested in checking out laptops from the library for short-term use within the library? Have you ever used the Libraries resources remotely?

-Yes:

Easier to take notes
Good at busy end of year

-No:

Lots of people bring their own
Too expensive, money can be used for books or journals

-Maybe, Depends on:

Battery life would have to be 4+ hours
Need excellent wireless throughout the whole library

Have you ever used an online/chat help desk to get assistance? Have you ever used the libraries online/chat service? If not, did you know it existed? Would you use it? If yes, what did you think of it? Have you ever used the libraries reference email service?

-No:

Need to Learn IM
I still use phone
Never used online help, just called, tired of email
Hate phones, use email

What services would make your research easier?

-Services:

Special Collections open more than 2 nights a week
Not enough access to other library's catalogues

Can Improve:

Journals and books are hard to locate online
Just bought Bookware, it searches all libraries' sites for you
Get articles using token method

Is there somewhere on your campus where some sort of library information kiosk and/or book drop would be helpful?

Information Kiosk:

-Yes:

Helpful when Library is far

-No:

Waste of resources

Book Drop:

-Yes:

Book drop would be good, especially on KGI, but the turnaround has to be quick
Have asked for 15 years
Very helpful

Do you use the libraries copy and printing services? What service would you like the copy center to offer? What hours?

-Services:

Quicker copy machines
Make pricing more competitive
New microfilm
Digitize microfilm!

-Location:

Should be more visible
Didn't know there was a copy center

-Hours:

Could be open more
Later hours

Any other comments?

-Positive:

Appreciate evolution over time
E-reserves

-Negative:

Noisy
Cold
Needs to be more inviting
If ordered on LINK+ twice, we should buy it
Worry about staff working without burnout
Old furniture and art

-Can Improve:

Food—even if only certain places
Tables outdoors
Wireless access outdoors
Need clearer labels on the doors
Need better layout

**Honnold Mudd Library
All Staff Survey Findings
August 22nd, 2005**

Table of Contents

Introduction.....2

All-Staff Survey Questions.....3

Synopsis of Findings.....4

Question #1: Redesign of Information/Reference Desk & Search Center6

Question #2: Improving services at Information/Reference Desk & Search Center.....8

Question #3: The new Welcome Desk.....10

Question #4: Requirement of working at the Welcome Desk 12

Question #5: How to improve services at Welcome Desk 14

Question #6: IT staff on duty..... 16

Question #7: How can Information/Reference Desk work better with other units18

Question #8: Lobby Elevator.....20

Introduction

The Honnold/Mudd Library has experienced several major changes in the past months. In the past couple of weeks several focus group sessions were conducted with different groups of library employees to gain a better understanding of how staff has been affected by the changes. Furthermore, an email based All Staff survey was conducted to gather more information in regards to the changes from staff that did not have an opportunity to participate in the focus groups or those who had more information to share. The survey questions were similar to the focus group questions and asked about the physical redesign, the internal work process between various desks, information technology, and the lobby elevator. A total of **26** staff members responded to the survey. Results of the all-staff survey are presented in this report and are organized by themes within questions. Like the focus groups, the objective of this survey is to highlight and present any likes/dislikes, issues, concerns, and suggestion staff has in regards to recent changes at the Honnold/Mudd Library.

All-Staff Survey Questions

1. Considering your job duties, what do you like most about the redesign of the Information/Reference Desk and Search Center? What do you like least about it?
2. What can be done to improve the help and services offered at the Information /Reference Desk? Please give specific examples.
3. What do you like about the new Welcome Desk? What do you not like about it?
4. Do you think all library staff should be required to work a shift at the Welcome Desk? Please explain why or why not.
5. What recommendations do you have for making the Welcome desk a better working place for staff as well as good service point for patrons? Please give specific examples.
6. How do you feel about having an IT person on duty in the search center? During what hours is it most important to have an IT staff person on duty?
7. Do you have suggestions how the Information & Reference Desk can work more smoothly with other library units?
8. Opening the lobby elevator to serve all floors has had a positive impact on the library in general, yet it is not perfect. Can you think of any negative impacts because of the opening of the lobby elevator?

Synopsis of Findings

A synopsis of the major themes that emerged from the survey analysis is presented below.

Major Themes:

Question 1: Redesign of Information/Reference Desk & Search Center

-Likes:

- Professional
- Better for Patrons
- Great to combine various services at a central location

-Dislikes

- Too big
- Unclear job roles/duties
- Physical structure has changed, but process still remain an issue

Question 2: How to improve services at Information/Reference Desk & Search Center

-Suggestions:

- Clarify each desk's and each staff/student worker's role
- Staff is "alienated" and does not work well together
- Across the board training for all desk workers

Question 3: The new Welcome Desk

-Likes:

- Creates a friendly/welcoming atmosphere
- Easier to assist patrons
- Provides security

-Dislikes

- Design, structure, and location issues
- Takes away valuable time from staff members
- Seen as a restriction to access rather than a welcoming area

Question 4: Requirement of working at the Welcome Desk

-Likes:

- More staff participation will decrease staffing issues
- Benefits staff members
- Reminds staff of the purpose of library—to serve patrons

-Dislikes

- Should be encouraged, not required
- Unclear processes and procedures along with unhelpful training
- Not a part of staff's job description

Question 5: How to improve services at Welcome Desk

-Suggestions:

- A detailed, clear, and organized manual/guidebook
- Shorter shifts
- Allow for other duties at desk when not busy
- Formal Welcome Desk specific training

Question 6: IT staff on duty

-Likes:

- Staff and patrons appreciate the expert help
- Good to have IT accessible
- Helps non-technology savvy staff

-Dislikes

- Clarify/designate a process/person to contact in IT
- IT should primarily train staff
- Staff or student workers should be available during all open hours

Question 7: How can Information/Reference Desk work better with other units

-Suggestions:

- Mainly an issue with staff, not student staff
- Inaccurate information is sometimes given to patrons
- Lack of communication and cooperation—"turf wars"
- Clarify roles/job duties
- Cross training on all basic functions

Question 8: Lobby Elevator

-Likes:

- Multi-level access
- Maximizes space and resources
- Has removed a barrier to access

-Dislikes

- Slow
- Not everyone uses their ID card
- Paces an extra burden on Welcome desk staff
- Unaware of what staff members are in the library
- Unclear button-to-location signage

Question # 1:

Considering your job duties, what do you like most about the redesign of the Information/Reference Desk and Search Center? What do you like least about it?

► Initial reactions:

- Not enough experience at the desk

► Likes:

-Design:

- Professional look
- Desk is more visible
- Artwork in the search center
- More room
- Closer to the gates which makes it more welcoming to patrons as they enter
- Patrons can easily see the desk

-Computer:

- The new flexible turn around monitors

-Roles/Job Duties:

- Good to have librarians working with student assistants
- Reference Librarians are now more visible

-Functionality:

- Great to combine two services in one desk
- Good to have multiple search centers
- Search Center has better lighting now
- Provides a one stop area for students to get assistance
- Most library services can now be found at a central area
- Easier for patrons to get a variety of information by stopping just at one desk
- Great for serving multiple patron needs from just one desk
- Patrons can go to one desk for help
- Desk is easier to find
- Allows the presence of IT staff

► Dislikes:

-Design:

- Bland
- Big/Huge
- Too remote from everything else
- Space behind the desk is wasted
- Arrangement of computer and phones on the desk
- Seating area for patron being assisted by a reference librarian is too small for leg room

-Computer:

- Distraction from welcoming students
- Lack of wireless access

-Roles/Job Duties:

- Confusion about who is supposed provide what information
- Who should the patron ask for help at the desk?
- Student workers receive complex questions and are expected to answer it
 - “We are expecting too much...students handle nearly all reference tasks”
- Repetitive training of student workers does not solve the problem of complex questions they receive
- Staff members of the different desks do not work well together which defeats the one desk approach
 - “Don’t work together easily...Physical space? Attitudes?”
- It is difficult to work with other staff members in this space

-Functionality:

- When desk staff are busy, patrons are hesitant to ask questions
- Seating of staff & librarians is not helpful to patrons
- Too much emphasis on entrance gate
- Librarians are too far away form the gates
- It is one desk by vision, but two desks by operation
- There is one desk physically, but this does not transfer to practice
- Too large for two workers
- The internal workings & ways of providing services at the desk have not changed
- Unclear were students should be silent and where they can talk
- Circulation desk was not included in the redesign process, although many of the changes have highly impacted that desk
 - Leaving Circulation out is “more than irksome”
- The large physical separation at the desk causes confusion for patrons as to who they should ask for help

► **Alternative suggestions:**

-Design:

- Place art and flowers on desk
- Needs decorations

-Functionality:

- Have one name for the desk instead of “Information/Reference” desk
- New desk should also encompass circulation to make it more user friendly
- Welcome desk greets incoming patrons, Information/Reference desk should not have to do so
- Work processes at the desk need to be examined and redesigned

-Roles/Job Duties:

- Cross training for those who serve at the desk
- Clarify who the patron should approach at the desk if they need help

Question # 2:

What can be done to improve the help and services offered at the Information/Reference Desk? Please give specific examples.

► Positive comments about current way of offering services:

-Service:

- We are doing a fine job
- Student assistants and LSA's have valuable knowledge staff can learn from

► Constructive comments:

-Roles/Job Duties:

- Clarify the roles and duties of each desk and each staff/student worker
- Training for all staff on all desk duties
- Expand training to cover various types of information
- Reference assistants need training on search center duties
- LSA's need training for appropriate referral
- Staff should be trained to look accessible and welcome patrons

-Functionality:

- All staff and student workers should know each other
 - "Alienation" does not serve our patrons well
- Stop monitoring the gate—Welcome desk does that
- Seat the Information desk person at the center facing the gate
- IT staff should be available at all times
- Both reference desks need a second monitor
- Reference Librarians and Information desk staff/students don't know each other
- Staff does not work together, they still operate as separate desks

-Service:

- Have an "on-call" librarian in the building
- Shorten the shifts
- Allow staff to bring work to desk
- Computer monitors are a barrier between staff and patrons
 - "Monitors could be put under the counter and be made viewable through the top"
- Personal computer use is distracting
- A connection/virtual line between the desk and library terminals
- Physically accompany a patron to help them locate books & materials
- Seek user feedback on a consistent basis and revise process and services accordingly

-Teamwork:

- End "turf wars," focus on service
 - "There are librarians who look down on info desk people and others"
- Remove the distinction of who answers what question
 - "Patrons aren't going to care...they will be understanding if an info desk person says 'you know that's best answered by the ref librarian on duty, let me get him/her for you.'"
- Everyone should be able and willing to answer basic questions

-Signage:

- Need for clear book location signage through out the library
- Need for clear entrance signage outside the library

Question # 3:

What do you like about the new Welcome Desk? What do you not like about it?

► Initial reactions:

- Not enough experience at the desk

► Likes:

-Design:

- Defines the entrance to the Honnold/Mud library
 - It has improved the “dark hole” at the entrance
- Visibility
- Height

-Public Service:

- Creates a friendly atmosphere
- Enjoy welcoming patrons
 - “It’s the best thing to come out of Redesign”
- Our Patrons appreciate it
- Good way for patrons to know more library staff members
- Easier to assist lost people (not necessarily patrons)

-Functionality:

- Provides security
- One can use the elevator instead of the stairs
- Great location for discussing immediate/ basic library questions with patrons

► Dislikes:

-Design:

- The card swipe is hard to find
- Too big
- Too tall
- Chair is too short
- The desk is too far out
 - “Would it work to angle the desk?”
- Can be made more attractive
- Short desk is ugly
 - Tall desk is “authoritative and detracts from the friendly atmosphere”
- People hide behind the lamp and computer/laptop
- Location and structure
- Sound/Noise at the desk carries up the stairs
- Very cold
- Dark

-Functionality:

- Boring
- Patrons just get on the elevator without using a card
- It does not offer enough services
- Does not address or solve the main problem of not knowing how to use the library

- “They (the students) think the library is lacking in user friendliness only because they don’t know how to use it...in spite of our good intentions and sincere efforts to be welcoming, student will still be negative...”

-Shifts:

- Interrupts the workday

-Purpose:

- Desk is designed to keep people out, not welcome them in
 - “Ridiculous forms, needing to keep track of who is in the building and who has forgotten a card, etc...”
- Monitoring access
- We restrict access
- Limitation of access is unwelcoming
- Purpose of desk is redundant

-Staff:

- Many staff members do not welcome patrons or make eye contact with them
- Overburdens staff member that have plenty other work to do
- Costs more money (wages) now and provides little benefits
- Welcome desk staff is isolated
 - “Safety concerns” and answering “routine questions”

► **Alternative suggestions:**

-Design:

- Take away the lamp
- Prohibit use of laptops
- Keep the desk clutter free

-Functionality:

- Moving the gate downstairs will reduce redundancy of the desk

-Shifts:

- Have 2 hour shifts

► **Points of disagreement:**

-Design:

- Polarized responses about height of desk, most either love or hate the high/short desk (one or the other)

Question # 4:

Do you think all library staff should be required to work a shift at the Welcome Desk? Please explain why or why not.

► Initial reactions:

- Not enough experience at the desk

► Yes:

-Participation:

- Have representatives from different departments serve at the desk
- More staff participation will solve staffing issues, especially during absence/vacation
- At least one hour per week
 - "...Reminds us why we're here and helps keep us in touch with our patrons"
- Librarians and circulation staff only
 - "...Will help the patrons recognize staff and feel comfortable asking for help"
- Everyone is capable of doing so
- Benefits staff members

-Role/Job Duties:

- Like welcoming people
- Desk duties should be included in new Librarians job description
- Nice to change duties for an hour

-Public service:

- Will establish a connection between staff and patrons

► No:

-Participation:

- Strongly encourage staff, don't require them (large emphasis on encouraging)
- Should not if they do not like that type of job
- Campus Librarians should not be required to
 - "It would give the message that users at Honnold are more important than users at the campus libraries"
- Those who dislike it will make patrons feel unwelcome
- Staff is already too busy
- Some feel uncomfortable

-Role/Job Duties:

- Dislike the day pass task
 - "It's one thing to sit there and say hi; it's quite another to be the door police"
- Some staff have other public service hours at other desks
 - "...No reason why they should be forced to take on additional hours of time taking away from other responsibilities"
- Only if specified on job description
- Some do not enjoy public service work
- Other duties, such as technical services, will suffer
- Staff not hired to perform public service duties

- "...Don't have the skills to direct/assist patrons properly"
- Some lack necessary skills
 - "Stressful both in the gate keeping function and in the wide range of knowledge required..."
- There are certain tasks only specific staff can do at the desk
- Takes staff away from duties only they can perform
 - For example "cataloging" and "digital projects"

-Public service:

- Staff already serve the public through assigned duties

► **Alternative suggestions:**

-Participation:

- Encourage, not require
 - "...People who won't/can't be effective in greeting the public"
- Only staff who enjoys welcoming students and gate keeping
- Only staff that has public service skills
- Create an incentive for working there
- Accommodate staff's workday to make participation easier

-Training:

- Provide complete and valuable training first
- Welcome desk volunteers can train staff
 - "A buddy system...might give hesitant staff the confidence to work at the Welcome desk"

-Role/Job Duties:

- If required, include standard back-up staffing plan for no-shows and or absence/sickness
- Clarify work process/procedures
- Should be included on future staff/librarian's job description
- Require those who have the knowledge and skills to work there instead of performing non-work related duties such as playing games in their offices

Question # 5:

What recommendations do you have for making the Welcome desk a better working place for staff as well as good service point for patrons? Please give specific examples.

► Positive comments about current way of offering services:

-Computer:

- Helps assist with searches and information

► Constructive comments:

-Manual/Guidebook:

- Provide more detailed and clear instructions/procedures
 - “Things are scratched and re-entered”
- Organize by function alphabetically
 - “Access,” “Day Pass,” “Guest,” “Link+” etc...

-Location:

- Move it back upstairs
- Combine it with the Information Desk

-Design:

- Have an ergonomic/adjustable chair
- Have a more attractive and comfortable desk
- Modify desk for better leg room
- Have normal/regular sized desk
- Better/more lighting
 - Such as an “OTT-LITE” task lamp
- Area should be sound proof
 - “Normal level” conversations “can be heard up to at least the third floor”
- Install security cameras
 - “Immediately” because library is open until 1:00am during the year
- Eliminate the turnstiles
- Place gates at the entrance and not on top of stairs

-Roles/Job Duties:

- Should be an “opportunity” to work there not an “obligation”
- One hour shifts only
 - Short shifts will “keep the staff enthusiastic”
- Need to have allowed duties for staff when desk is not busy
- Unclear as to if staff can do their own work at desk

-Functionality:

- Not an important service point
- Simplify, combine and reduce amount of forms
 - “Too much of the information is duplicative...and I always have to rifle through the entire pile to find the one I am looking for”

-Training:

- Formal training for Welcome Desk duties
- Provide PR skills training
- Person at desk should know more information about the different campuses in order to answer questions appropriately

-Service:

- Provide appropriate staffing plans including backup for absence & tardiness
- Relax library admittance rules
 - Monitoring “can be done in a less intrusive manner”
 - “Staff members who forget their id card should be treated with more respect”
 - “If the person working at the welcome desk knows who you are, then they should be able to hand you a day pass without filling out the green card”
 - More strict entrance causes waiting lines; “We don’t want users to rename it the waiting desk”

-Staff behavior:

- Staff members should allow person at desk to do his/her job
 - For example: don’t engage in long, unnecessary conversations
- Staff members should pay attention and welcome incoming patrons

-Computer:

- Eliminate the computers/laptops
 - Some staff members “huddle behind the screen”
- Person at desk should be greeting, not working on a computer
- Have a specific welcome desk computer with necessary tools
- Is used for playing games

Question # 6:

How do you feel about having an IT person on duty in the search center? During what hours is it most important to have an IT staff person on duty?

► Positive comments:

-Service:

- It's great!
 - "It is very important that a frustrated student not have to wait for someone to come down from IT—if there is even anyone there"
- Staff and patrons appreciate the help and support

-Accessibility:

- Accessibility and visibility of IT is good
- Great to have Joel office near by

-Expertise:

- We need to have IT to help with technological problems
- Good because non-IT staff does not have the expertise to help with technology issues
- Non-IT staff can learn from them
- Good for those who are not technology savvy

► Constructive comments:

-Service:

- Rumors that IT will only be able to answer certain questions
 - That is "ridiculous"
- Clarify procedures for contact in IT
- Good, but all staff should be able to answer basic IT questions
 - "...There are always questions about laptops, connectivity, and problems with the equipment in the Search Center"
- Some times they don't respond to email
- Who do we call at IT if help is needed
- Have a designated IT contact person specifically for patron questions

-Unnecessary:

- No, IT staff should not be at the search center
 - "They should engage in training staff ...and develop better systems...if IT people have to be present at all times, systems are too complex"
- Most questions can be handled by regular staff
 - "...We keep hiring IT people...do they not have enough to do?"
- Presence of IT should not be used by staff as a way to refuse learning technology
- Unnecessary to have them there unless it is busy

► Alternative suggestions:

-Hours:

- Needs to be staffed during all open hours
- When search center is busy
- When search center is open

- Afternoons, evenings, and weekends
- Late afternoons, late evenings, and late weekends
 - “Many of our users want timely technology help—they don’t want to come back a day later during regular business hours”
 - “Early morning and late night users usually know what they are doing”
- Evenings
- 12:00 noon to 9:00 pm
- Outside the normal 9-5 business hours
 - “During regular business hours, we can easily check with IT upstairs”
- 4:00 pm to closing
- 2:00 pm –9:00 pm, seven days a week
- If unable to staff all open hours, staff “student hours” 10am to closing
- As many hours as possible

-Staffing:

- Needs to always be staffed, whether by a staff member or student
- Have IT staff during normal working hours and student staff at other hours
- Have IT on the spot
- Have IT on call, “within a three minute wait” during open hours

Question # 7:

Do you have suggestions how the Information & Reference Desk can work more smoothly with other library units?

► Positive Comments:

-Interaction:

- Conscious effort by staff to acknowledge presence of other staff members
- Student staff work with each other and staff great
- There are no problems between desks

► Constructive Comments:

-Interaction:

- This is mainly an issue with regular staff, not student staff
- Don't know/Can't remember all the rules of all the desks
- Lack of communication between the Information/Reference desk and Circulation

-Service:

- Not everyone at the desk gives accurate information

► Suggestions:

-Interaction:

- Increase communication
- Increase cooperation
- Everyone has specialized knowledge that other can learn from
- The "Shadows" program can address this question
- Communicate new information immediately to all desks
- Have more personalized methods of dispersing information
 - Emails are fine but "a personal touch" such as "an open house type of event" can energize staff

-Roles/Job Duties:

- Desk staff should have an "in depth" understanding of the library and our services
 - "For example, what BAS does, and how everything fits in with everything else"
- Reporting lines and activities of librarians should be clarified and examined
- Have one supervisor/coordinator for that desk
- More sharing of knowledge instead of just "refer/defer"
- Mandate a semester long commitment for staff at the desk
 - This should increase the "willing to learn how to help patrons"
- Post work schedules of all desk staff on the all-staff calendars
- Clarify who should be contacted for which questions
- Clear and deep understanding of interfaces
- Certain questions can be answered by anyone
 - Staff at different desks should answer a question as long as they can

-Training:

- Have a general training session soon about policy and procedures of various desks

- This “would help other Library Units understand what is expected and why they do so - of what they do at that desk”
- Training on the basics of serving at the desk
- Training modules would help
- Group training sessions
 - “Everyone is hearing the same information at the same time”

Question # 8:

Opening the lobby elevator to serve all floors has had a positive impact on the library in general, yet it is not perfect. Can you think of any negative impacts because of the opening of the lobby elevator?

► Positive comments:

- It's great
- It's about time
- Having it closed was a "barrier" that has been removed
- Maximizes use of library space and resources
- Having multi-level access from the lobby is great

► Constructive comments:

-Staff:

- Can not see librarians, Reference, Information, or Circulation staff leave
- Places a "bell-ringer" burden on Welcome Desk staff

-Usability:

- Very slow
- Decrease the time for the doors to open
- Many patrons do not use ID card and enter the library
- Security issues
- Possibility of patrons skipping the check out procedure all together
 - "They can take materials from the library, get onto the elevator to go directly to the first floor"
- Is being used by many who don't require using it
 - Increases wait time times
- Confusion as to what patrons should do
 - Some patrons "swipe their card at the welcome Desk and then head up the stairs...I have also seen (college) staff head straight for the elevator without swiping an ID card
- Slow when used for transporting items such as carts, paint, etc...
- Potential negative effect on disabled patrons if it was to go out of order

-Signage:

- Unclear what button inside elevator leads to what floor/area
- Clear and more maps/directories of content of each floor
- Unclear which buttons to push

-Book locations:

- Needs Call number location guides

Final Survey Findings

USER SURVEY

December 2005

Total Respondents=171

1. *Why did you come to Honnold/Mudd Library today?*
Most frequent responses: to get books, make copies, work on papers, do research, study

- 2A. *Do you like the redesign of the search center?*
Yes 44%
No 4%
Didn't Notice 52%

- 2B. *What do you like about the redesign of the search center?*
Most frequent response was N/A (because respondent didn't notice the change)
Others liked its accessibility, the computers, and that it was easier to use

- 2C. *What don't you like about it?*
Most frequent response was N/A. Very few negative comments.

- 3A. *Did you use the Reference/Information desk at Honnold/Mudd today?*
Yes 44%
No 56%

- 3B. *Why or why not?*
Most frequent response: No need, didn't need help, etc. Those who did use the desk wanted help mainly with research or finding books. However, many of those who didn't stop at the desk still answered 3C affirmatively—referring instead to a prior experience.

- 3C. *Did you receive good service?*
Yes 65%
No 2%
N/A 33%

4. *Did you know that the Libraries offer live online Chat Reference?*
Yes 50%
No 50%

- 5A. *Do you feel comfortable finding your way around Honnold/Mudd Library?*
Yes 84%
No 15%
N/A 2%

- 5B. *How could we make it easier to find you way around the library?*
Even if respondents answered "yes" for 5A (as most did), they still felt a need for more maps and signs more prominently placed.

6A. *Do you like the new Welcome Desk at the entrance of Honnold/Mudd Library?*
Yes 86%
No 6%
N/A 8%

6B. *What do you like or dislike about the Welcome Desk?*
Very few respondents disliked the Welcome Desk. Most found its staff helpful and friendly.

7. *Did you find what you were looking for today?*
Yes 91%
No 4%
N/A 5%

8. *What could have made your experience at Honnold/Mudd Library a better one?*
While many requested “more” (books, online articles, amenities like food and coffee, etc.), many described the experience as “great” and felt that nothing needed to be changed.

9. **AFFILIATION**

CGU	33	19%
CMC	35	20%
CST	1	1%
CUC	4	2%
HMC	3	2%
PIT	17	10%
POM	40	23%
SCR	38	22%
Total	171	100%

10. **STATUS**

Faculty	1	1%
Staff	2	1%
Student	133	78%
Blank	35	20%
Total	171	100%